

INTRODUCING NEW MODULE IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING USING CDIO: CASE STUDY

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Abstract

The CDIO Initiative (www.cdio.org) is an innovative educational framework for producing the next generation of engineers. Throughout the world, collaborators have adopted CDIO as the framework of their curricular planning and continual improvement of their educational programs. In SP, the DCHE Course Management Team (CMT) had used the 12 CDIO Standards in a self-evaluation process aim at identifying areas of improvement in the curriculum. This paper is the second part of a 2-part submission for ISATE2014 in which we outlined and present a case study used by the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) of Singapore Polytechnic (SP) in designing a new Year 3 free elective module entitled *Chemical Process Operations and Troubleshooting* using the CDIO approach. In this paper, we illustrates how Part 4 of the CDIO syllabus corresponds with different stages of module development, its benefits and how the 12 CDIO standards supplements the existing guidance documents in Singapore Polytechnic's (SP) existing Academic Quality Management System (AQMS) from the stages of module development to module delivery, evaluation and improvement. The module feedback and semestral results obtained from the pilot run of the module suggests that the CDIO way of module design and development fits well with our AQMS, that the focused and systematic way of designing and delivering the module had enhanced students' learning experiences, which makes learning of an engineering module enjoyable, meaningful and at the same time allowing them to score excellent semestral results. Lastly, this paper also highlights how the CDIO standards have guided the module team in pinpointing the right skills and competencies needed to deliver the module prepared so as to ensure that students continue to be well prepared and equipped with the relevant knowledge and skills in addition to the critical C-D-I-O and CDIO skills to be work, life and world ready in the constantly changing global climate.

Keywords: *CDIO, module design, continual improvement, chemical engineering*

Introduction

Cheah & Koh (2014) have shown the close matching between module design and development and C-D-I-O (i.e. Conceive – Design – Implement – Operate), and that the same CDIO standards can be used to assist lecturers in designing a new module. In the case of *Chemical Process Operations and Troubleshooting*, the DCHE Course Management Team (CMT) recognized from the results of its scan of external environment (namely feedback from the chemical processing industry and graduates working in these industries) that its present coverage of troubleshooting skills is inadequate. There is a cohort of 20-30 students who did not further their studies and are working as process technicians in the chemical processing industries. Having worked as chemical engineers in the past, we can quite readily pen down the intended learning outcomes for process operations and troubleshooting. We also identified the necessary skill set needed, including teamwork, communication, problem-solving and critical thinking.

An internal scan of the curriculum showed that although the fundamental knowledge and skills in process troubleshooting are covered throughout the course, they are scattered among individual core modules and are hence "tagged" to those modules. Although the students received 6-weeks industrial internship training at the Chemical Process Technology Centre (CPTC) on Jurong Island during their second year vacation; there is room to further enhance students' competencies in process operations and troubleshooting. What we needed is an integrated pilot plant that can aid students in acquiring these learning outcomes. We also noted that most process operations training needed by the industry require potentially hazardous, costly and bulky equipment beyond the affordance of SP, the team ascertained that the best method to build our students' competency in these areas is via dynamic simulations of integrated industrial processes. The CMT therefore decided that a new module is needed to be offered as free elective to this cohort of students. The next step is to design the module proper.

Module Design Using CDIO Standards

Cheah, Koh & Ng (2013) had earlier reported on the use of the 12 CDIO Standards for reviewing the DCHE course for continual improvement. We now take the process one step further in using the very same standards to guide us in our design of the new 60-hour module *Chemical Process Operations and Troubleshooting*. Table 1 shows how the 12 CDIO Standards are applied in the design on this new module.

Table 1. Application of CDIO Standards in module design

CDIO Standard	Application of standard in designing <i>Chemical Process Operations and Troubleshooting</i>
Standard 1 CDIO as Context	This content of this module is very relevant to the chemical processing industry, with the learning tasks centered on mainly on the “I” and “O” aspects. The tasks are designed to mimic real-world working environment encountered by a chemical engineering technologist.
Standard 2 CDIO Syllabus Outcomes	The module aims focus on attainment of specific skills identified in the “need analysis” mentioned earlier, Cheah and Koh (2014). They are also consistent with the overall DCHE Course Aims; which in turn are aligned to the SP Holistic Education graduate attributes in being work-ready.
Standard 3 Integrated Curriculum	Lecture is kept to a minimum of 1 hour per week (hpw), and tutorials (2 hpw) are designed to be highly interactive using cooperative learning strategy. On the technical aspects, this module integrates knowledge from other DCHE core modules such as <i>Heat Transfer & Equipment, Separation Processes, Process Instrumentation & Control, Plant Safety & Loss Prevention and Workplace Safety & Health for Chemical Engineers</i> , etc. Various CDIO skills are integrated as well, especially in the laboratory-based learning tasks.
Standard 4 Introduction to Engineering	Not applicable for this module.
Standard 5 Design-Implement Experiences	Not applicable for this module.

Standard 6 CDIO Workspaces	A new integrated pilot plant specifically designed by the first author was acquired, and relevant lab space allocated. Virtual workspace will also be utilized in the form of dynamic simulation of chemical processes.
Standard 7 Integrated Learning Experiences	Four laboratory-based learning tasks were designed to support the integrated curriculum mentioned above. Two are based on an integrated pilot plant and another two are based on virtual chemical plants in the EnVision dynamic simulation system.
Standard 8 Active Learning	All the learning tasks mentioned above uses active and experiential learning, using scenario-based learning widely adopted in various DCHE core modules.
Standard 9 Enhancement of Faculty CDIO Skills	The first author who is the module coordinator of this module had been mentored by the second author when he first joined the service; and had introduced CDIO in another module that he coordinated earlier. They had earlier published a joint paper in the 2013 International CDIO Conference. The teaching team supporting this module also consists of staff already familiar with the DCHE “CDIO-way” of training students.
Standard 10 Enhancement of Faculty Teaching Skills	
Standard 11 CDIO Skills Assessment	The assessment (both CDIO skills and chemical engineering knowledge) is part of the integrated learning experiences mentioned above.
Standard 12 CDIO Program Evaluation	The module was reviewed after one semester of its introduction in Semester 2 AY2013/14.

Discussion on Work Done

To facilitate active and experiential learning of the new module, four learning tasks were developed as follows:

1. Prepare process equipment for maintenance work (planning phase)
2. Prepare process equipment for maintenance work (execution phase)
3. Operate and Troubleshoot a Natural Draft Furnace System
4. Operate and Troubleshoot an Amine Treating Unit

Tasks 1 and 2 are based on a new integrated pilot plant that was designed by the first author and purchased using F&E funding. Task 1 is intended to expose students to the real-world work of process technicians in readying the plant for shutdown and maintenance work (planning of isolation, shutdown, purging procedures, preparing all necessary paperwork like permit to work, isolation and blind lists, risk assessment, toolbox talk, etc); while Task 2 is a follow-up from Task 1 whereby students will execute their planned procedures in Task 1 to safely shut down and prepare the plant for maintenance work. Tasks 3 and 4 use virtual chemical plant based on the EnVision dynamic simulation system (see Figure 1) which was purchased earlier. These tasks simulate the real-world operation of chemical plants and offer students opportunity in dealing with plant start-up, shutdown, steady state operations and process upsets. Both simulation models were chosen because firstly, they are common processes in chemical process operations which they may likely operate in the future. Secondly, both processes are generally easy to comprehend yet at the same time they provide students with sufficient challenge and opportunities to troubleshoot process changes and upsets, thus honing their problem solving and troubleshooting skills.

Figure 1. Dynamic simulation model for Amine Treating Unit (ATU) showing the Amine Stripper

Results and Discussion

The module was first piloted as a free elective to Year 3 students in Semester 2, Academic Year 2013/2014. A total of 49 students took this module. Feedback on the module was conducted to obtain students input on their learning experience. Students were asked to evaluate the following:

- Q1. This module was **well taught**.
- Q2. The course **materials** in this module were of high quality.
- Q3. The **workload** in this module was manageable.
- Q4. Requirements for completing the **assessment** tasks in this module were clear.
- Q5. This module has better prepared me to work in the chemical process **industry**.

- Q6. I will **recommend** this module to my juniors and peers.
- Q7. Overall, how would you **rate** this module?
- Q8. What were the **best** aspects of this module?
- Q9. What aspects of this module were most in need of **improvement**?

The results for the quantitative feedback components (Q1 to Q7) on a scale from 1 (lowest) to 10 (highest) are shown in Table 2. Each of the scores were analysed to assist the module teaching team in identifying the key areas which were done well, evaluate the outcomes of module design using CDIO standards, and to identify the areas for improvement (Standard 12).

Table 2. Module feedback for pilot run of *Chemical Process Operations and Troubleshooting*

Question	Max Score	Score obtained
1	10	9.10
2		7.96
3		8.64
4		8.76
5		8.86
6		9.20
7		8.64
Average score		8.74

The high score of 9.10 that the module was well taught is an indication that the teaching and assessment of the module using CDIO approach (Standard 9) was well received by the students. This conclusion was echoed in a separate teaching feedback of this module on the module coordinator/ lecturer that was conducted on the same group of students and a similar score of 9.18 was obtained. This module was able to integrate knowledge across multiple DCHE modules (Standard 3), including various CDIO skills (Standard 7). Students were given opportunities to experience the integration of process operations and troubleshooting with other DCHE modules like *Chemical Reaction Engineering*, *Workplace Safety and Health for Chemical Engineers*, *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*, *Process Instrumentation and Control and Separation Processes*, etc. This allows students to sum up and apply the underpinning knowledge learnt from previous modules to operate integrated chemical processes. The integrated curriculum and learning experiences as well as the application of CDIO approach in teaching and assessment have produced excellent semestral results in the pilot run of the module with 87.8 % of students scoring quality grades of Distinction, A and B+.

One aspect to highlight in the teaching and learning of this module was that even though greater emphasis were placed on the demonstration of the module's performance criteria, students were ironically given "opportunities to fail" in the practical tasks both during lab and simulation works. Bearing in mind that there are often "no unique solutions" in chemical process

operations and troubleshooting, students were given chances to stretch their thinking and apply basic underpinning knowledge acquired to actively experiment different techniques and strategies, for example, to prepare process equipment for maintenance work. No “model answers” were given to the students, but rather, any feasible answer or proposal will be accepted (even though there might be imperfections). Hence, feedback was provided to the students on each lesson to help them identify these imperfections in their proposed solutions (if any) and how they can be improved, all of which are done with no penalty imposed, mainly with the intention to help them learn from their mistakes. While students were given the “opportunity to fail”, we are mindful that when students make mistakes when performing their tasks (especially when it is safety, conduct related due to negligence or lack of due diligence), students will still be penalized. However, when such penalties were given, students were made to reflect on the reasons why they were penalized and in most cases, students were able to identify and accept the penalty for their own mistakes. Through such reflections, we also aim to help students integrate their knowledge and skills in the areas of workplace safety and health, cooperative learning, teamwork and CDIO skills, etc during the learning of daily tasks as a chemical engineer. A picture showing students performing a utility-tie-in connection using piping and fitting assembled by themselves is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Students performing utility-tie-in using piping and fitting assembled by themselves

The course materials were developed with the intention to mimic as close as possible to the industry practices in process operations and troubleshooting. The new integrated pilot plant and simulation software utilized aimed to provide CDIO workspaces to enhance the integrated learning experiences of the students (Standards 6 and 7). However, it was noted that students’ feedback on the quality of teaching materials had comparatively received the lowest score among all module feedback components. One observation made by the first author when teaching this module was that students, being less experienced, require more guidance than expected to comprehend the key concepts of the module, especially in the areas of understanding the

rationale behind the process control techniques during operation and troubleshooting scenarios. As a result, more time and effort were dedicated to provide students with opportunities to actively experiment the cause and effects of different control actions (Standard 8). The learning materials were also revised concurrently when teaching the module as oral feedback were collected from students on a regular basis on their learning experiences (via interaction during and beyond lesson time), and adjustments were then made to suit the students’ learning pace and capabilities. Students, knowing that the module was piloted for the first time, were generally open to provide honest feedback, and they understood that the truthful feedback provided was a win-win situation for them and the subsequent batches of students to improve their learning experiences in the module. However, it was inevitable and noticed that the revision of the learning materials when the module is ongoing might have resulted in confusion and frustration (at times) in some students from the unlearning and relearning of several concepts. The module team takes the comparatively lower feedback score for this component positively, as it highlights the key areas of improvement for the module, which will be discussed in the next section.

The workload of this module is generally manageable by the students. Being a practical based module, the aim of this module is to mimic real world working environment encountered by a chemical engineering technologist to better prepare our graduates to be work ready (Standard 2). Thus, in contrast to traditional DCHE module which is weighted heavily on written tests and examinations, a greater assessment weightage was allocated to lab work and practical test ($\approx 50\%$). To sustain interest and motivation in the module, no “homework” was given to the students. Instead, formative assessments in the form of mini weekly quizzes were given to the students at the end of each lesson. The main objective of the mini quizzes was to reinforce the key concepts learnt in each lesson, and questions were mainly in the form of multiple choice, short structured, fill in the blanks and true/false. To encourage students’ participation in the quizzes, a weightage of 10% to the final grade was allocated. To close the learning loop, feedback was provided to the students on each question in the quizzes so that they were able to learn from their mistakes (if any). The results of the mini quizzes were encouraging with the cohort scoring an average of 90.4%. Being motivated to learn the module contents and to score in the quizzes, this module also received excellent punctuality and attendance records with 86.0% of students having perfect punctuality and attendance in the entire semester. Oral feedback was also obtained from the students during the course of the semester and the feedback provided was consistent with the module feedback results that the workload is manageable by the students. The excellent semestral results obtained also suggest that the module’s performance criteria were attainable.

In the area of clear communication of assessment requirements, the score of 8.74 achieved could be attributed to the following factors: firstly, there was clear explanation of the assessment criteria of the module from Day One, with constant reminders and reinforcement that students are assessed not just on technical knowledge, but also on CDIO skills (Standard 11). Secondly, the weekly mini quizzes help students develop clearer understanding of the key concepts in the module, both in the written and practical assessments. Thirdly, there are detailed learning outcomes, assessment rubrics and guidelines provided; this is especially helpful in the area of practical assessment. To better prepare students for the practical test, assessment rubrics which clearly indicate the assessment components and weightages for each performance criteria were specified to the students. The feedback obtained from students was that the given assessment components provided them with clearer learning checkpoints to better assist them in the revision process. These are in line with Standards 1, 2, 8 and 11.

In terms of whether the students find that they were better prepared to work in the industry after reading the module and whether they will recommend the module to their peers and juniors, the high scores of 8.86 and 9.20 respectively was an encouraging sign that this module has met its primary objective to equip students with the key competencies and confidence to work in the industry (Standard 2). The overall module feedback average score of 8.74 suggests that the students have excellent overall impression of the module and its learning experiences. Some positive comments (extracted from the module feedback) provided by the students include:

"It is a more hands on module rather than a theoretical module which is great as it tests us students on our practical knowledge and how well we understand the system rather than pure memorizing"

"The best aspect of this module is that it is very relevant to the chemical process industry. It can help us to connect the concept and theory learnt in other modules to the operation of a chemical plant. Also, this allow student to experience how a chemical process technician handle problem, upset or emergency situation in a process plant. Personally, I feel that this module will benefit the students in the long run."

"Students are able to learn and experience what a chemical engineer does in their daily life. Learning the theory isn't enough, one must understand what they are doing to be able to understand why they are learning other modules. If a chemical engineer doesn't know how the plant works, he won't be able to improve the plant."

Based on the quantitative module feedback scores and qualitative feedback obtained, we are encouraged and hence daringly conclude that the success of this module's pilot run is attributed to the integrated curriculum and learning experiences (Standards 3 and 7), CDIO spaces (Standard 6), and that this module has

helped students prepare for real world challenges as a chemical engineer to be work ready (Standards 1 and 2) via active learning (Standard 8).

Recommendations for Future Work

While we were encouraged that the pilot run of Chemical Process Operations and Troubleshooting module yielded excellent module and teaching feedback scores, we recognize that there are areas for improvement based on feedback by the teaching team and students' module feedback (Standard 12). The key comments highlighted in the students' module feedback were as follows:

1. Increase the time duration spent on learning the simulation to perform start-up, shut down and troubleshooting exercises.
2. Increase the module hours as there are a lot of simulation exercises for students to try.
3. Students who lacked plant experience during internship at CPTC might require more help in class and more detailed explanation on the equipment and utilities.
4. The notes are not really that useful as this is a module that requires more understanding.

The feedback to increase the module hours or time spent on learning the simulation was the most common feedback provided by the students. One observation made when teaching the module was that students were generally able to keep up with the pace during the earlier chapters which were less practically intensive and students might have some prior exposure when they attended internship at CPTC. However, when the module progresses to the simulation activities, the lesson pace became slower than expected as it was initially presumed that CPTC training has provided students with sufficient foundation knowledge in plant operations to enable students to apply them to grasp the skills in process troubleshooting with greater ease. This gap between the expected and actual presumed knowledge and skills levels had caused some hiccups during the lesson delivery. The learning materials were hence revised along the way to suit the learning needs of the students.

Rather than increasing the hours for the module, one possible suggestion to resolve points (1), (2) and (3) is to consider merging and integrating chemical process operations and troubleshooting with existing DCHE modules. One possibility is to merge it with *Process Instrumentation and Control*. As operation and troubleshooting of integrated processes requires knowledge and skills in process instrumentation and control, merging the two modules may be able to exploit the synergy between them to achieve the desired learning outcomes in both modules in a shorter total duration in contrast with teaching both subject areas as separate modules. In order to get a stronger affirmation whether this is a feasible direction, it is recommended to run the module on a second batch of students to confirm

the similar observation and findings before deliberating this at DCHE CMT for further discussions.

The module coordinator (who is also the first author) agrees that the quality of the teaching and learning materials can be further improved. It was mentioned in the previous section that improvements were made to the teaching and learning materials during the course of study when the module was piloted. While the teaching team agrees with the student's module feedback that because of the practical nature of this module which places more emphasis on understanding rather than memory work, the lecture notes might be perceived by the students to be lacking in detailed explanations. This lack of detailed explanations, or we put it across as spoon feeding, is compensated to the students in the tutorial and lab exercises where students were made to demonstrate the learning outcomes of the modules by performing actual lab and simulation tasks as opposed to regurgitating model answers from lecture notes in most "traditional" theoretical modules. While we recognize that improving teaching and learning materials is an ongoing process and new learning strategies might be developed for different batches of students, we are also mindful that it is critical to set the right mind-set among the students' right from day one. The mind-set that there could have no "model answers to memorize" must be strongly brought across to the students right from the start, that the purpose of the lecture notes and tutorial materials is to merely serve as a tool or guide to help students to grasp the key underpinning knowledge before they could apply them to different plant operating scenarios. The learning materials should not be regarded as a secret manual for them to memorize to excel in the module.

Lastly, while the pilot run of the module has yielded successful students results and module feedback, the sustained success of the module and its relevance to the industry can only be achieved if the teaching team continues to "sharpen its saw" to stay current with the current industry processes and practices, namely in the areas of new emerging processes like green engineering, workplace safety and health practices, permit to work systems, utility tie in techniques and equipment. Staff industrial attachments to local or overseas process facilities at least once every three to five years will be advantageous for the teaching team to stay current with these practices to ensure that students continue to be well prepared and equipped with the relevant knowledge and skills in addition to the critical C-D-I-O and CDIO skills to be work, life and world ready in the constantly changing global climate.

Conclusions

We shared our approach in using the CDIO Standards to guide us in designing a new free elective module, *Chemical Process Operations and Troubleshooting* for DCHE. We felt that using this approach offers 2 benefits: (1) Focused: The 12 CDIO Standards supplements the existing guidance documents in AQMS by providing specific guidance in core areas,

for example module development (e.g. integrated curriculum), delivery (active learning), assessment and evaluation; and (2) Systematic: The 12 CDIO Standards allows the module to be developed in a systematic fashion according to the Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate stages, namely in the areas of module development to module delivery and finally module evaluation and improvement. The module feedback and semestral results obtained suggest that the CDIO way of module design and development fits well with our AQMS. It also serves as a checklist to guide the lecturer in the process, and that this focused and systematic way of designing and delivering the module had enhanced students' learning experiences, which makes learning of an engineering module enjoyable and meaningful. Finally it helps the module team pinpoint the right skills and competencies needed to deliver the module contents prepared.

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